

ABA, LAB 173711, or a combination of LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis had fully recovered 23 d after treatment. Pretreatment with tetcyclacis alone produced intermediate effects.

Chilling reduced leaf photosynthesis in all treatments, most drastically in untreated controls (90% reduction after 2 d recovery) (see figure). Differences among treatments were most significant after 9 d recovery: photosynthetic rates had returned to the original values in plants pretreated with both LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis; control values were lower by 60%. Pretreatment with LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis led to significantly faster recovery than did pretreatment with ABA or LAB 173711 alone.

Chemical analogs of ABA, particularly in combination with tetcyclacis, represent a potentially powerful tool to prevent chilling injury in rice plants. □

Changes in net photosynthetic rate (A) in IR36 rice plants during recovery from 2 d chilling at 5 °C, IRRI, 1988. Means ± SE of 8 measurements.

Adverse soils tolerance

Effect of salinity on rice germination and seedling growth

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We evaluated the relative salinity tolerance of BG350 an improved variety commonly grown on saline soils. Salinity-tolerant traditional variety Pokkali was the check.

Irrigation water (EC 0.25 dS/m) was used as the laboratory medium. Electrical conductivity was adjusted to 0.25, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 dS/m by adding table salt. Twenty seeds were kept in each solution in petri dishes, with three replications. Water volume was maintained by adding solution.

Effect of salinity on rice root and shoot growth. Weerawila, Sri Lanka.

EC (dS/m)	Root length (cm)		Seedling height (cm)	
	BG350	Pokkali	BG350	Pokkali
0.25	2.1	5.9	2.1	4.6
1.0	2.4	3.9	2.2	4.2
2.0	2.3	3.5	2.5	3.5
3.0	1.5	2.5	2.3	2.5
4.0	1.0	1.7	2.0	1.6
6.0	0.6	1.0	1.3	0.6
8.0	Traces		0.6	1.0
LSD (0.05)	0.30	0.61	0.59	0.59

After 5 d, germinated seeds were counted and root length and seedling height measured.

BG350 performance was similar to that of salinity-tolerant Pokkali (see table). No seeds germinated at EC 10 and 12 dS/m. All seeds germinated at

EC 8 dS/m and below.

Root length decreased significantly at EC 2 dS/m and above. Neither variety produced roots at EC 8 dS/m. Seedling height decreased significantly at salinity levels above EC 4 dS/m. □

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